

MARINE MONITORING IN THE NEW YORK BIGHT

Dennis J. Suszkowski and Edward D. Santoro

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
Marine and Wetlands Protection Branch
26 Federal Plaza
New York City, New York 10278

1. INTRODUCTION

The ocean environment in the New York Metropolitan area has always received much public attention. In recent years problems associated with fisheries, water quality, beach quality and ocean dumping of wastes have moved into the forefront of public awareness. Part of EPA's task is to oversee a number of permitted activities which encompass these issues including dredged material dumping and woodburning at sea (in conjunction with COE issued permits). In addition sewage sludge, acid waste, industrial and cellar dirt dumping and beach water quality monitoring are all items regulated and monitored by EPA. The present paper discusses some of the major monitoring elements associated with these programs.

2. OCEAN DISPOSAL/PERMIT MONITORING

As presented in Figure 1 there are 7 designated dumpsites in or near the New York Bight. The New York Bight is a 11,000 square nautical mile area from Cape May, New Jersey to Montauk Point, New York and about 100 nautical miles seaward to the edge of the continental shelf. Unquestionably, the greatest variety of barge/vessel dumped wastes in the country occurs in this region. From 1973 to 1982, approximately 60-100 percent of all industrial and municipal waste ocean dumping occurred at these sites (Anderson 1983). In addition, 5-15 percent of all dredged material activities in the U.S. occurs in the Bight. The quantities of materials ocean dumped at these sites is listed in Table 1.

Subsequent to the enactment of the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act (MPRSA) in 1972 as amended in 1977. EPA is charged with evaluation of marine environmental impact of these dumping activities in addition to other factors. The respective field monitoring programs associated with ocean dumpsites covered under the MPRSA are as follows:

Dredged Material

The present dredged material dumpsite was established in 1914, although other material of this type was dumped at inshore sites since 1888. Since 1980, this site has been split into four quadrants with one quadrant used for capped material and the others used in stepwise manner when each is filled. The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers has the permitting authority while EPA

oversees the program. Monitoring that has occurred at the site has primarily been periodic bathymetric surveys and special designed studies for example - capping studies.

Woodburning Site

The Region currently has in effect four permits to dispose of wastewood from piers, hulks and wrecks by burning at sea. The wood incineration site was established in 1968 (Fig. 1). The resultant ashes are returned for appropriate land disposal. EPA required the major woodburning applicant, the Corps of Engineers; to perform a specially designed study in which high volume air samplers were mounted on vessels upwind and downwind of these burn barges. Air samples were

Figure 1. Ocean Dumpsites currently utilized in EPA Region II. Insert depicts 106 Mile industrial and sewage sludge sites.

of sludge disposal currently phasing in use of DMSDS for sewage gathering baseline information at this new site is of paramount importance. EPA is committed to perform baseline and trend monitoring at this site before, during and after sludge disposal to ascertain environmental impact associated with these wastes. The monitoring sites associated with these efforts appear in Figure 3. Over the past three years, EPA has performed research cruises in and around this large site at these and other stations located off the continental shelf. Currently the baseline monitoring is done at six stations where surface and subthermocline water samples for organics, trace metals, water quality and microbiology sediment samples are taken at 2 sites. Bioaccumulation studies are to be done at 5 sites along the shelf slope break (Figure 3). In addition, endangered species observers are aboard the research vessel to document the presence of these species in the area. Although final permits for site use have not been prepared, EPA anticipates that applicant monitoring at this site will include tracking of the waste plumes and water quality and pollutant analyses at the site. EPA has developed a tiered approach to sampling this site. Near field pollutant concentrations will be assayed and, as a function of a wasteload categorization, will be estimated for areas downstream of the site for compliance with Water Quality Criteria. In the event that a potential acute or sublethal threshold could be reached, downstream monitoring would be done.

Cellar Dirt Site

The cellar dirt dumpsite (see Fig. 1) was established at its present site in 1940. Over the period 1981-1985, no dumping has occurred at this site. In 1985 NYC utilized this site for disposal of approximately 50,000 cubic yards of material from the Marine Transfer Terminal in New York City. Presently, EPA has an application for disposal of cellar dirt material from the Port Liberte Project. Draft monitoring plans to be performed by the applicant include three surveys over two years at seven sites in and around the dumpsite. Monitoring will encompass water column chemistries, planktonic and benthic biota identification, and examination of trace metals content of sediments and organisms. Hydrodynamics and water mass movements will also be studied if the permit to discharge is granted.

3. NON PERMIT RELATED MONITORING

Ocean Water Quality

Although the thrust of the sampling programs outlined above include a water quality component, EPA also monitors water quality of beaches in the region outside of specific permit activities. The beach Station Network consists of 66 stations along the New Jersey and Long Island, New York Coasts. Samples are gathered for bacteriological water quality on a weekly basis from those ocean stations which run along the coast from Cape May point to along the South Shore of Long Island to

Figure 2. New York Bight transect stations.

Shinnecock Inlet.

The presence of bacteria in ocean waters at bathing beaches has been a cause for concern for many years. The quality of water along New Jersey and Long Island beaches is of obvious importance to the flourishing tourist industry of both states. Over the years it has been very rare that bathing beaches have been closed by local health officials in relationship to the presence of sewage-related materials, including pathogenic organisms. In 1985, after a severe rainstorm, beaches in Monmouth and Cape May Counties were closed by local officials because of recorded elevated concentrations of coliform bacteria in selected areas.

During the past two summers, algal blooms have been responsible for extensive areas of greenish colored water off the central to southern New Jersey coast and along the south shore of Long Island. These blooms were most intense from the beach out to about a half-mile, but frequently extended out to about three miles and persisted from August through most of September. The primary reason for concern about the green tide by the public is the diminished aesthetic value of the coastal waters. However, reports also indicate that bathing in algal bloom affected waters can cause a number of skin reactions and respiratory complaints. During these "green tide" blooms bathers have experienced various symptoms including nausea, sore throat, eye irritation, fatigue, dizziness, fever and lung congestion. Other individuals were affected by

Figure 3. Proposed nearfield sampling stations at the 106 Mile municipal sewage sludge site the large square represents the site. (●) depicts water column chemistry & microbiology stations, bioaccumulation study sites are denoted by (▲), Benthic infauna community studies and sediment chemistry and microbiology sites (□).

odors associated with the green water. As the organic matter decomposes, the algae produces hydrogen sulfide gas. These foul odors have also been associated with low dissolved oxygen levels in the waters.

In view of the extensive public concern for this issue, EPA has taken the initiative to set up an interagency committee comprised of EPA, New Jersey Department of Environmental Protection (NJDEP), National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and others to examine this issue and set priorities for future monitoring efforts.

Anoxic Events

A major incident occurred in 1976 and involved large scale oxygen depletion in much of the bottom waters of the entire New York Bight (Swanson & Sindermann, 1979). This event was also accompanied by massive wash-ups of floatables along the beaches of Long Island. Since 1976, bottom waters in the New York Bight have experienced anoxic conditions. However, the problems have generally been localized to much smaller areas than the 1976 episode. In response to the 1976 anoxia event, a New Bight Advisory Committee

was formed and is composed of representatives from EPA, NOAA, NJDEP, NYCDEC, the Coast Guard and the counties of Nassau and Suffolk on Long Island. The purpose of forming the committee was to promote an open dialogue and exchange of information between all agencies. In particular, monitoring programs of the agencies could be coordinated to provide the greatest economy of resources devoted to monitoring environmental problems in the New York Bight. From time to time, various members of the committee have met on an Ad Hoc basis in an attempt to address specific issues.

Regarding dissolved oxygen, EPA has a series of helicopter sampling stations along 12 transects perpendicular to the shores of Long Island and New Jersey. These transects extend from the New Jersey (9 transects) and Long Island coasts (3 transects) and are comprised of 5 and 4 stations per transect respectively (Braun and Petrus, 1986). These are sampled on a regular basis during the summer months. The stations are presented in Figure 4. These stations were established to gather near-surface and near bottom dissolved oxygen values in critical bight areas. Prior agreements with NOAA allow for these samples to mesh with others taken in conjunction with their ongoing MESA and other programs (Braun & Petrus 1986). In addition to the EPA program, NOAA conducts intensive surveys along a transect off the New Jersey coast in the vicinity of Long Branch. NJDEP has also provided monitoring support in the waters of southern New Jersey. Routine bacteria sampling of water offshore of the Bight Apex has also been accomplished by EPA helicopter. Due to the problems encountered last summer, NJDEP in coordination with EPA, the NJ Department of Health, and the Jersey Shore County Health Officers, has developed a monitoring protocol which will provide health officials with pertinent information to determine whether beaches should be closed due to elevated bacteria levels.

Routine weekly collection of phytoplankton samples at 9 stations along the New Jersey coast and 26 stations along the Long Island coast has been accomplished by EPA helicopter. Samples have been given to NJDEP and Nassau County Department of Health for identification and quantification of species. In addition nutrient levels of total phosphorus, phosphate phosphorus, ammonia nitrogen, nitrate nitrogen and silica are ascertained for these samples. Since the green tide episode of last summer, EPA, NJDEP and NOAA have been meeting over the past few months in order to develop a strategy for monitoring and potential research into the causes of green tide, which can be implemented this summer.

The work that has been done in the past by agencies of the New York Bight Advisory Committee has principally been monitoring activities. Work already programmed for this summer also is largely committed to monitoring activities. The nearshore water quality conditions in the New York Bight last summer, particularly along the New Jersey coast, were of enormous public interest. Present monitoring plans will be capable of detecting

problems. In the case of bacteria, decisions will be able to be made to close beaches as appropriate. For dissolved oxygen and "green tide", currently programmed monitoring will not greatly enhance our understanding of the causative factors involved in these problems. New resource commitments are necessary in order to fully determine causative agents.

4. POTENTIAL FOR ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

In addition to the monitoring described above, EPA enforces data collection which characterizes all wastes dumped both by chemical analyses and physical parameters, such as grain sizes where applicable.

Also, EPA has taken the position that the criteria which classifies wastes as environmentally acceptable for ocean dumping incorporate limits stringent enough to ensure that materials being dumped are harmless when dumped in the ocean for bulk discharges of liquids, solids or mixtures. The primary regulatory tests are acute toxicity tests run for 96 hours on three trophic levels planktonic, crustacean and fish species. The regulations provide that within 4 hours after dumping the concentration within the zone of

Figure 4. Helicopter transect sampling stations, after Braun & Petrus (1986).

initial mixing must be reduced to less than .01% of the acute toxicity of the waste. EPA's marine water quality criteria must also be met.

Solid phase bioassays are also run to assess the acute toxicity and the bioaccumulation potential of the dumped wastes on at least three trophic levels of benthic organisms, usually shrimp, mollusc and a polychaete. If there is no statistical difference at the 95% confidence interval between controls and test organisms in both toxicity and bio-accumulations and greater than 90% control survivals, then the material is acceptable for ocean disposal.

5. SUMMARY

As can be seen from the above, EPA Region II remains committed to continue monitoring activities for the varied uses of the oceans throughout the area. EPA Region II has developed these monitoring programs based upon regulatory requirements. We have found that utilizing working groups reduces conflicts between regional and national monitoring goals, and produces a more useful and beneficial product on which to better regulate man's activities in the ocean waters of the region.

However, monitoring is only a part of the issue which require consideration for these ongoing activities. EPA also provides surveillance activity in concert with the U.S. Coast Guard. Spot inspections by EPA field teams provide additional waste analyses and toxicity testing to assure permit compliance. It is hoped that through these efforts the ocean can remain a safe and enjoyable place for all.

6. REFERENCES

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